

Table 2. Effect of heat treatment on germination and field emergence of seed of 15 widely grown commercial indica cultivars in Latin America, 1987.^a

Cultivar	Origin	Germination in laboratory (%)				Field emergence (%)								
		Initial ^b		8 mo		Initial		5 mo		8 mo				
		No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 3 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 3 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 3 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 3 d	No treatment	55 °C, 65 °C, 3 d			
Anayansi	Panama	91	100	80	83	76	73	73	57	60	52	52	52	48
Araure 2	Venezuela	91	98	81	83	83	65	70	54	53	53	66	52	48
BR-IRGA409	Brazil, Guatemala	95	99	88	82	85	74	71	49	49	49	66	47	48
CICA4	Various countries	92	100	87	83	81	69	76	59	56	52	69	45	47
CICA8	Various countries	93	98	83	82	82	64	68	59	56	46	65	50	50
CICA9	Paraguay, Dominican Republic	93	93	81	79	76	73	66	58	60	50	54	53	49
CR1113	Costa Rica	92	99	85	85	85	72	87	60	59	54	67	57	52
Diwani	Surinam	82	93	81	79	80	63	64	49	50	46	56	50	49
INIAP7	Ecuador	92	93	78	86	80	70	67	52	52	53	51	49	49
INTI	Peru	93	99	78	81	82	74	76	56	61	57	57	59	49
JUMA50	Dominican Republic	93	99	85	83	81	83	72	54	54	56	58	53	54
Metica 1	Colombia, Brazil	90	98	87	77	72	79	73	46	54	46	43	51	42
Oryzica 1	Various countries	88	93	79	84	74	66	65	49	49	45	57	45	45
Sinaloa A80	Mexico	95	100	86	87	86	80	73	65	59	54	65	54	52
Tikal2	Guatemala	93	91	76	86	82	75	72	55	58	48	42	50	45
Mean		91.5	97.2	82.3	82.7	80.3	71.5	71.2	68.5	54.8	55.3	50.7	53.8	48.5

^aAnalysis of variance^c

F (treatment) df = 3

F (variety) df = 15

F (treatment × variety)

Error mean square

^aMean of 3 replications, 200 seeds/replication. ^bAll cultivars had 100% germination under both heat treatments. ^c*** = significant at *P* = 0.01, * = significant at *P* = 0.05, ns = not significant.

42.5**

51.5**

6.1**

2.08

ns

2.01*

ns

10.3

ns

ns

ns

ns

ns

ns

50.4**

6.3**

3.6**

9.2

Sheath blight diseases in tropical ricefields

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The several kinds of sheath diseases of rice, usually caused by fungus pathogens, produce different types of sclerotia. Their pathogenicity and occurrence have been reported in Japan, China, America, and other places, but little is known about their distribution, frequency, and significance in tropical rice-growing areas. We surveyed their distribution patterns in relation to rice sheath disease incidence in 1985.

Sclerotia extracted from soil samples from several fields were examined under a dissecting microscope. They were identified by size, shape, and color. Distribution frequencies were calculated.

Pure cultures of fungal sclerotia isolated were grown on potato dextrose

therapy (65 °C, 6 d) on the viability of seed of 15 commonly grown Latin American rice varieties. Germination (in petri plates) and field emergence of seed kept at 65 °C for 6 d were compared with those of seed kept at 55 °C for 3 d to break dormancy and with untreated seed. Readings were taken immediately after treatment (1 mo after harvest) and after 5 and 8 mo of post-treatment storage at room temperature. Because hot water therapy has little effect on germination and viability in most varieties, it was not included in the viability studies.

Even after 8 mo of room storage, the treatments differed little in germination, most being around 80% (Table 2). The slight negative effect on field emergence was not enough to prevent a good stand.

The choice of seed treatment depends on the *Pseudomonas* species involved, available facilities; quantity of seed to be treated, and its destination or use. For seed for international exchange and for genetic or basic seed, heat treatment is relatively easy. For commercial certified seed, treatment with kasugamycin could greatly reduce contamination with *P. fuscovaginae* and offer some protection against leaf blast in the seedling stage. □

agar at 25 °C for 4 d to use as inocula. Plants of rice cultivar IR36 were inoculated at both seedling and early maturity stages. Lesion appearance and size were observed to determine their virulence.

Three pathogenic sclerotia-producing fungus pathogens — *Rhizoctonia solani*, *R. oryzae-sativae*, and *R. oryzae* were identified. The frequencies of the inoculum extracted from the soil were 57.3% for *R. solani*, 42.3% for *R. oryzae-sativae*, and 0.4% for *R. oryzae* (see table).

Tests for pathogenicity indicated that *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were more aggressive on rice than *R. oryzae-sativae*. They infected rice plants at both seedling and adult stages; *R. oryzae-sativae* infected plants only at the adult stage. Symptoms caused by *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were similar, but *R. oryzae* caused dark reddish brown or brown margins. The lesions caused by *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were also much

Distribution of sclerotial populations responsible for sheath diseases of rice in the tropics. IRRI, 1985.

Site and population	<i>R. solani</i>		<i>R. oryzae-sativae</i>		<i>R. oryzae</i>	
	no.	Frequency (%)	no.	Frequency (%)	no.	Frequency (%)
C14						
Population A	111	53.6	96	46.4	—	—
Population B	110	52.1	101	47.9	—	—
Combined	221	52.9	197	47.1	—	—
B40						
Block A						
Apr	67	53.6	57	45.6		10.8
May	57	64.8	30	34.1	1	1.1
Block B						
Apr	74	65.5	38	33.6	1	0.9
May	64	64.7	35	35.3	—	—
Total or av	483	57.3	357	42.3	3	0.4

larger than those by *R. oryzae-sativae*, which were aggregated small spots.

We concluded that *R. solani* is the major causal organism of sheath diseases of rice in the tropics. Although less aggressive on rice than the two other fungi, *R. oryzae-sativae* was a

relatively large part of the entire sclerotial population found and may play an important role in causing rice sheath diseases in tropical areas. *R. oryzae* is very virulent on rice, but its sclerotial population was relatively low. □

Effect of plant age at inoculation on rice tungro virus development

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Twenty 10- to 20-d-old plants of variety TN1 were inoculated using 5 green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* per plant after 24-h acquisition feeding.

Susceptibility was high in 10-d-old plants, with percentage of infection decreasing with increased plant age (see

Relationship between plant age, infection (%), and incubation period.

figure). The negative correlation between plant age and infection percentage was highly significant. Mean incubation

period progressively increased with plant age. These two factors were positively correlated. □

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater rice in Orissa, India

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Rice, the principal crop of Orissa, is grown in habitats ranging from fully rainfed unbanded uplands to deepwater situations with more than 50 cm water for the major part of the year.

Deepwater situations exist not only in the coastal belt at mean sea level (MSL) but also at altitudes as high as 1,067 m above MSL in the interior districts. The varieties grown under such situations are all local and take more than 180 d to mature.

In a survey of plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater rice in Orissa India.

Nematode species	Frequency (%)	Density
<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	25	L
<i>Helicotylenchus dihystra</i>	20	L
<i>H. crenacauda</i>	25	L-M
<i>Hemicriconemoides cocophilus</i>	5	L
<i>Hirschmanniella mucronata</i>	65	M-H
<i>H. oryzae</i>	5	M
<i>Hoplolaimus indicus</i>	15	L
<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp.	5	H
<i>Pratylenchus zeae</i> ^b	10	L

^a L < 100 nematodes/250 ml soil, M = 100-250 nematodes/250 ml soil, H > 250 nematodes/250 ml soil. ^bNew record.

rice in Cuttack, Balasore (coastal belt), and Koraput (high altitude) districts, nine species were found (see table).

Hemicriconemoides cocophilus and *Pratylenchus zeae* were prevalent in the